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SUSTAINABLE COOLING AND STORAGE SYSTEMS: A CASE STUDY IN A BIOFUELS PLANT IN GREECE

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ABSTRACT

The present paper concentrates on the implementation of an absorption cooling system in the MIL OIL biofuels plant in Central Macedonia, Greece, aiming to meet the cooling needs of the biodiesel production line and the digester. At the design point, the low-temperature cooling load, the high-temperature cooling load, and the coefficient of performance are equal to 200 kW_c, 240 kW_c, and 0.84, respectively. Furthermore, a digital twin tool will be developed to simulate, control, and optimize the performance of the absorption chiller. Finally, it is highlighted that the utilization of a cold water storage tank volume of 30 m³ improves the digester cooling performance, enhancing the cooling coverage from 68.81% to 79.33%, during the summer period.

Keywords: Waste heat recovery, biofuels, industry, absorption cooling, thermal energy storage

INTRODUCTION

Industrial activities represent a major share of global energy consumption, primarily due to their intensive demand for heat, cooling, and electricity. Due to environmental concerns, the development of innovative and sustainable solutions to cover the industrial energy needs is vital. The utilization of waste heat from industrial processes, as well as the integration of renewable energy technologies and energy storage systems, can increase overall energy efficiency, promote the decarbonization of the industries, enhance process flexibility, and lower greenhouse gas emissions [1].

Absorption chiller is one of the most predominant cooling technologies in the field of waste heat recovery and renewable energy sources. Indicatively, Cui et al. [2] examined a triple-stage LiBr-H₂O absorption chiller, driven by waste heat coming from a data center at a temperature of about 50°C. The design cooling load was 50 kW_c. The implementation of that system reduced the mechanical cooling load by 80.5 % and the electricity consumption by 78.0 MWh_{el}. Additionally, Sow and Grosu [3] investigated energetically and exergically a single-effect LiBr-H₂O absorption cooling system, using climate data from France and Senegal. The maximum values of the coefficient of performance (COP) and the exergy efficiency were determined at 0.76 and 56%, respectively. Furthermore, the absorption cooling cycles can be integrated into multiple energy production installations in the industrial sector. More specifically, Mahmoudkhani et al. [4] analyzed a combined cooling, heat, and power (CCHP) unit thermodynamically, economically, and environmentally, which was powered by waste heat in a cement plant. The configuration included a Rankine cycle and an absorption chiller. According to the final results, the overall energy efficiency was determined to be 30.2%, the overall exergy efficiency was 28.7%, the capital cost was 661 k\$, the payback period was 6.18 years, and the sustainability index was 0.1216.

According to the existing literature review, the research community has focused on the integration of absorption chillers into industrial facilities, coupling them with industrial processes and other energy production systems. The current work presents an absorption cooling system powered by waste and solar heat in a biofuels plant in Northern Greece. The operation of the proposed cooling unit will be supported by a Digital Twin (DT) tool. Moreover, the novelty of the present study is enhanced by the investigation of the integration of a cooling storage tank, coupled with the absorption chiller, to improve the digester cooling performance during the summer months.

PLANT DESCRIPTION

The MIL OIL plant is located in the industrial zone of Serres in Central Macedonia, Greece, and produces biodiesel and biogas. The produced biogas is burned in three combined heat and power (CHP) units, two with an electrical load of 1067 kW_{el} and another larger one with a power output of 1562 kW_{el}. It's worth noting that significant amounts of heat are generated from the cooling circuit and the exhaust gases of the CHP units. With all 3 CHP units operational, the hot water stream available for utilization is at a temperature level of 99-100°C, with a maximum

The cooling coverage (CC) is defined as the ratio of the actual cooling production (Y_{cool}) to the theoretical cooling production under nominal conditions ($Y_{cool,nominal}$):

$$CC = \frac{Y_{cool}}{Y_{cool,nominal}} \quad (3)$$

All the integrated systems, including the absorption chiller and the storage tanks, are modelled in MATLAB software. The ambient temperature data is coming from the Photovoltaic Geographical Information System (PVGIS).

RESULTS OF THE ABSORPTION CHILLER DESIGN POINT

At the design point of the absorption chiller, the three main input parameters of the system, which are the hot water inlet temperature, the hot water volume flow rate, and the ambient temperature, are equal to 100°C, 22.5 m³/h, and 20°C, respectively. According to the results, the generator heat input is calculated at 524 kW_{th}, the LT cooling load at 200 kW_c, the HT cooling load at 240 kW_c, the COP of the chiller at 0.84, the absorber thermal load at 502 kW_{th}, the condenser thermal load at 452 kW_{th}, and the generator temperature at 90°C.

OPERATIONAL MAP-DIGITAL TWIN

A DT tool will be developed to optimize the operation of the absorption chiller. This tool will be fed with real-time input data from the plant's SCADA / EMS. The input data will be measured and monitored by sensors and Internet of Things (IoT) devices. The outputs of the DT tool, such as the cooling production and the COP, will be also monitored to assess the cooling production process. The inputs of the DT tool include: i) hot water inlet temperature from the CHP units and the solar thermal panels, ii) hot water volume flow rate from the CHP units and the solar thermal panels, and iii) ambient temperature. The DT will be trained considering various values of the input parameters. For the training set, the input parameters lie within specific ranges, i.e., the hot water inlet temperature ranges from 90 to 100°C, the hot water volume flow rate from 20 to 25 m³/h, and the ambient temperature from -5 to 40°C. The calculated outputs are the LT cooling load in [kW_c], the HT cooling load in [kW_c], and the COP. All the outputs of the training set of the input parameters are used to create an operational map for the absorption chiller. The operational map, along with multi-dimensional regression strategies, will be used to develop the DT tool. Indicatively, the results of the cooling load, and the COP for different hot water inlet and ambient temperature levels when the hot water volume flow rate is equal to 22.5 m³/h (nominal value) are depicted in Fig. 3. The operational map can determine the cooling production and the COP values for all the testing sets of input parameters in the examined ranges.

Fig. 3. Results of the cooling loads (a), and the COP (b) for different hot water inlet and ambient temperature levels when the hot water volume flow rate is equal to 22.5 m³/h (nominal value).

To ensure that the absorption chiller operates in a highly efficient way and meets the plant operator's needs, including forecasted cooling needs and hot water properties, various quantities, such as flow rates, temperatures, and pressure levels, are properly controlled, receiving appropriate signals and actuation suggestions from the DT. For instance, the mass flow rate of the chilled water, the cooling water, and the LiBr solution can be controlled through the rotational speed of the respective pumps.

RESULTS OF THE INTEGRATION OF COOLING STORAGE

A cooling storage tank to improve the digester cooling performance is investigated in this section. As shown in Fig. 4a, the COP decreases significantly when the ambient temperature increases, especially in daylight hours. According to the final results, which can be found in Table 1, the utilization of a 30 m³ tank provides high coverage of the cooling needs, which is found at 79.33% during the summer period. Additionally, the proposed storage system avoids unnecessary capital cost and space requirements of larger tanks, and offers a good balance between technical performance and investment feasibility, making it the most suitable choice. This storage solution can provide the

nominal digester cooling load for additional hours during the day, in comparison with a typical configuration without any storage system, as illustrated in Fig. 4b.

Table 1. Results of the integration of a cooling storage tank, along with the tank costs, during the summer period (June-August).

Cooling storage tank volume (m ³)	-	10	20	30	40	50
Digester cooling production (MWh)	252.19	272.43	283.90	290.75	293.49	294.75
Digester cooling coverage	68.81%	74.33%	77.46%	79.33%	80.07%	80.47%
Storage tank cost (€)	-	13,000	18,200	22,000	26,000	29,900

Fig. 4. Ambient temperature and COP (a), and a comparative diagram of digester cooling load when the cooling storage tank is not used and when a cooling storage tank volume of 30 m³ is integrated (b) on the 21st of July.

CONCLUSIONS

The main conclusions are listed below:

- A low-temperature cooling load of 200 kW_c, a high-temperature cooling load of 240 kW_c, and a coefficient of performance of 0.84 are computed at the design point.
- The digital twin tool will provide real-time monitoring of the system operation, as well as control and operational strategies, supporting the plant operator.
- The implementation of a cold water storage tank volume of 30 m³ enhances the digester cooling coverage from 68.81% to 79.33% during the summer months.

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